

Supporting Information

Reconfigurable optical sensor for metal-ion mediated label-free recognition of different biomolecular targets

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Figure S1. Optical characterization of PSiO₂ scaffolds upon GLYMO-IDA silanization. Reflectance spectra recorded in air on a PSiO₂ scaffold oxidized at 750 °C for 1 h before and after GLYMO-IDA silanization for different times, namely 30 min, 1 and 2 hours.

Figure S2. Optical characterization of GLYMO-IDA functionalized PSiO₂ scaffolds after interaction with different metal-ions. Reflectance spectra recorded after GLYMO-IDA functionalized PSiO₂ samples exposure to different metal-ion (Cu²⁺, Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Fe³⁺) solutions.

Figure S3. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy of GLYMO-IDA functionalized PSiO₂ scaffolds after interaction with different metal-ions. High-definition N 1s spectra of A) GLYMO-IDA, B) Cu²⁺/GLYMO-IDA, C) Zn²⁺/GLYMO-IDA, D) Ni²⁺/GLYMO-IDA, E) Fe³⁺/GLYMO-IDA. Spectra are fitted and charging corrected.

Figure S4. Effect of metal ion concentration on CAR detection. A) Changes in the effective optical thickness (EOT) of PSiO₂ scaffolds functionalized with Cu²⁺ ions at different concentrations ranging from 0.025 to 0.2 M, upon exposure to 1 mM of CAR. EOT₀ refers to pure buffer (n=2). B) Effective optical thickness (EOT) measured on a PSiO₂ sensor after various functionalization and sensing steps, upon exposure Cu²⁺ solutions at concentrations from 0.025 to 0.2 M. Specifically, EOT values were measured upon grafting of GLYMO-IDA, Cu²⁺ chelation, binding of CAR (1 mM), CAR removal by HCl washing, Cu²⁺ removal in EDTA solution for each Cu²⁺ concentration tested.

Figure S5. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy characterization of carnosine binding on sensor. High-definition spectra of A) Cu 2p and B) N 1s regions recorded before (red line) and after (blue line) the incubation of the sensor with carnosine.

Figure S6. Optical detection of carnosine different concentrations on A) Cu^{2+} /GLYMO-IDA and B) Zn^{2+} /GLYMO-IDA functionalized PSiO_2 scaffolds. Reflectance spectra recorded before (red spectrum) and after sensor exposure to increasing carnosine concentrations.

Figure S7. Repeatability of the sensor toward CAR detection. Sensor response (calculated as $EOT - EOT_0$) recorded for three different measurements using the same sensor ($n=3$).

Figure S8. Optical characterization of Fe³⁺/GLYMO-IDA functionalized PSiO₂ scaffolds in ATP detection tests. Reflectance spectra recorded after sensor exposure to increasing ATP concentrations.

Figure S9. Calibration curve of carnosine by HPLC measurements. Calibration curve obtained from the HPLC analysis of carnosine standard solutions (5-500 µM).

Sample	N 1s	
	BE (eV)	Area (%)
GLYMO-IDA	400.0±0.06	100.0±0.0
GLYMO-IDA-Cu ²⁺	400.7±0.06	70.6±1.9
	402.2±0.15	29.4±1.9
GLYMO-IDA-Zn ²⁺	400.3±0.06	86.1±2.8
	402.2±0.12	13.9±2.8
GLYMO-IDA-Fe ³⁺	400.2±0.06	88.1±1.0
	402.2±0.06	11.9±1.0
GLYMO-IDA-Ni ²⁺	400.2±0.15	81.3±1.0
	401.8±0.20	18.7±1.0

Table S1. XPS results of N 1s signal fitting on GLYMO-IDA P₂SiO₂ scaffolds before and after metal ions complexation.